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THE TIME DEPENDENT SCHRÖDINGER EQUATION IN A STRONG LASER FIELD

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1 INTRODUCTION

Laser-matter interaction is one of the main topics in current physical research, due to the fact that lasers enable the study of matter under various physical conditions. For instance the interactions of lasers with plasmas, solid state matter as well as warm dense matter (WDM) are currently vivid research subjects. Laser interactions not only extended our understanding of matter itself, it also opens up possibilities for a wide range of applications. Cheaper and more effective cancer therapy and laser particle acceleration are promising outlooks [1, 2].

Lasers are also utilized to create WDM. For the production of WDM, laser shock waves are shot at a target, which will create highly compressed states of mega-bar pressures and temperatures on a scale of several electron volts [3, 4]. To probe WDM, lasers can be used for wide or small angle x-ray scattering analysis, also absorption spectroscopy and many other applications regarding this subject. Laser-driven plasma acceleration does not only hold a potential application to medical treatments, but in the area of material science, where lasers could facilitate a deeper implantation of multiple ion species in semiconductors [5]. In nuclear fusion research, lasers can compress the fusion pellet directly or indirectly. Ignition of the fusion reaction is then possible either due to the shock conditions or a additional external driver like electron or ion beams, which themselves are accelerated using powerful lasers [5]. A different, yet powerful, laser concept is the free-electron laser (FEL). The basic principle of FELs is the emittance of synchrotron radiation from relativistic electrons by sending them into an undulator. Thus, the electrons start to oscillate and emit light down to wavelengths on the x-ray spectrum [6]. FELs capable of emitting such wavelengths are called XFELs. Those kind of FELs are not only of interest in physical research, but also find applications in e.g. biological research [7]. Facilities featuring such XFELs are for instance the Lineac Coherent Light Source (LCLS) in Stanford [8] or, by the end of 2016, the European XFEL facility at DESY in Hamburg [9]. Usual laser concepts can be grouped, by the length of their emitted pulses, into ultra-short and long-pulse lasers. An example of an ultra-short pulse laser is the Dresden laser acceleration source (DRACO) at the Helmholtz Zentrum Dresden Rossendorf (HZDR) [10]. These kind of lasers are often deployed for laser particle acceleration research. Long-pulse lasers are used for the ignition of plasmas, as in the NIF facility. Other examples for long-pulse lasers are the n- and phelix [11, 12] at the GSI in Darmstadt or the Orion laser in Aldermaston [13]. The scale of those long laser pulses is about several nanoseconds, whereas short-pulse lasers have typical pulse lengths of several femtoseconds.

The physical effects of laser matter interaction include the creation of Auger electrons, where a laser pulse pulls out an inner shell electron and causes the relaxation of an outer shell electron to the unoccupied energy level. This relaxation causes the emission of another electron, the so called Auger electron, without the emittance of any radiation [14]. The Auger electron effect already shows that lasers are able to ionize atoms, where an electron essentially becomes free through the interaction with a laser field. This can lead to further effects like the recombination of electrons with ions, which can cause the emission of photons as the so called radiative recombination. Lasers also are able to interact with free electrons by inelastic scattering. Electrons can get excited to higher energy levels by inelastic laser scattering, afterwards this excited state relaxes into its initial energy level by the emission of a photon [14]. In addition to all those bound electron laser interactions as examples of inelastic scattering, elastic scattering of bound electrons is possible as well. A large part of the x-ray scattering spectrum is the elastic peak, which is caused by elastic interactions of bound electrons with x-ray wavelength photons. This means,

that bound electrons oscillate in the laser field and emit light of the same frequency. That is the case, if the photon energy does not match the transition energy. In general, laser emissions are able to lift bound states to higher energy levels. Furthermore lasers enable lowering of potential barriers, enabling a bound particle to tunnel through [15]. All of those effects are experimentally observed and broaden our knowledge about matter. Measurements of these physical effects are standard nowadays. However, it is very challenging to temporally resolve the processes, as they happen on atto- to femto-second time scales. Simulating those physical processes enables us to see the fundamental process behind experimental observations, and enhance the way theory and experiment complement each other. Especially, effects like ionization or state transitions are only well understood, if one is able to exactly explain what is happening and how well the theory behind those processes predict the experimental outcome on those microscopic scales. As one tries to explain a non relativistic quantum mechanical system, the starting point of all models is the Schrödinger Equation. Thus, the main subject of this thesis is to find a general way to simulate a one-dimensional quantum system in a strong time-dependent potential.

2 THEORETICAL PRELIMINARY

The first chapter covers the theoretical foundations of the Time Dependent Schrödinger Equation (TDSE) and its form in a strong laser-field. After the statement of the problem, the atomic unit system is introduced, as a method to achieve a dimensionless form of the TDSE. To evolve a wave-function in time, the time evolution operator is introduced. The next section of this chapter is a simplification of the one dimensional hydrogen problem, which features a singularity caused by the coulomb potential. For this reason a model potential is introduced and discussed. In the last section a time disturbance term is proposed.

2.1 THE TIME DEPENDENT SCHRÖDINGER EQUATION

The TDSE describes the quantum state $|\psi\rangle$ as well as its time evolution. Since it is a postulate, it cannot be derived, but shown to satisfy the minimal action principle [16]. Without any vector potential, the spatial representation of the TDSE for a particle in an arbitrary potential is

$$i \hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \psi(\vec{r}, t) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \Delta \psi(\vec{r}, t) + V(\vec{r}, t) \psi(\vec{r}, t), \quad (2.1.1)$$

where \hbar is the reduced Planck constant, Δ is the Laplacian Operator and m refers to the mass of the particle. To interpret $|\psi(\vec{r}, t)|^2$ as a probability density within the Copenhagen interpretation of Quantum Mechanics, it has to full fill the norm condition

$$\langle \psi | \psi \rangle = \int_V d^3r \psi^*(\vec{r}, t) \psi(\vec{r}, t) = 1, \quad (2.1.2)$$

where V refers to the volume of the system. The Schrödinger Equation is only able to describe quantum systems in the non-relativistic regime, see Ref. [17].

2.2 THE DIMENSIONLESS SCHRÖDINGER EQUATION

For numerical calculations it is useful to transform Eq. (2.1.1) into a dimensionless form. One way to do this is to choose the atomic unit system:

1. $m_e = 9.1 \cdot 10^{-31} \text{ kg} = 1 \text{ a. u. of mass}$
2. $e = 1.6 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ C} = 1 \text{ a.u. of electric charge}$

3. $\hbar = 1.05 \cdot 10^{-34} \text{ Js} = 1 \text{ a.u. of action}$
4. $4\pi\epsilon_0 = 1.1 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ F/m} = 1 \text{ a.u. of permeability}$

From this starting point, the following quantities are derived:

- $a_0 = \frac{4\pi\epsilon_0\hbar^2}{m_e e^2}$ the first Bohr-radius as 1 a.u. to measure length
- $E_{\text{Hartree}} = \frac{\hbar^2}{m_e a_0^2}$ the Hartree energy as 1 a.u. to measure energy
- $t_0 = \frac{\hbar}{E_{\text{Hartree}}} = \frac{m_e a_0^2}{\hbar}$ as 1 a.u. to measure time

A common and useful example of atomic units is the Hamiltonian featuring a Coulomb potential

$$\hat{H} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e} \Delta - \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 |\vec{r}|} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e} \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \right) - \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}}. \quad (2.2.1)$$

Recalling the definitions above

$$\hbar = m_e = 4\pi\epsilon_0 = e = a_0 = 1 \text{ a.u.},$$

the following expression is obtained

$$\hat{H} = -\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \right) - \frac{1}{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}}. \quad (2.2.2)$$

Now the atomic units can be used to rewrite Eq. (2.1.1), where the Hamiltonian \hat{H} has the just derived form

$$i \frac{\partial \psi(\vec{r}, t)}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{2} \Delta \psi(\vec{r}, t) - \frac{\psi(\vec{r}, t)}{|\vec{r}|}. \quad (2.2.3)$$

2.3 THE TIME EVOLUTION OPERATOR

It is possible to define an operator $U(t, t_0)$, which transforms a state $|\psi(t_0)\rangle$ at time t_0 into a state $|\psi(t)\rangle$ at time t

$$|\psi(t)\rangle = U(t, t_0) |\psi(t_0)\rangle. \quad (2.3.1)$$

It can be shown that $U(t, t_0)$ is unitary and preserves the norm of the state. Inserting the above definition into Eq. (2.1.1) results in an equation to determine the form of $U(t, t_0)$.

$$i \hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} U(t, t_0) |\psi(t_0)\rangle = \hat{H}(t) U(t, t_0) |\psi(t_0)\rangle \quad (2.3.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} U(t, t_0) |\psi(t_0)\rangle = -\frac{i}{\hbar} \hat{H}(t) U(t, t_0) |\psi(t_0)\rangle. \quad (2.3.3)$$

The last line can be viewed as a differential equation for the time evolution operator (see Ref. [17, pp. 308 sq.]),

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} U(t, t_0) + \frac{i}{\hbar} \hat{H}(t) U(t, t_0) = 0. \quad (2.3.4)$$

If \hat{H} is time-independent, the solution of Eq. (2.3.4) is

$$U(t, t_0) = e^{-\frac{i(t-t_0)\hat{H}}{\hbar}}. \quad (2.3.5)$$

The problem of finding a solution for Eq. (2.1.1) is now reduced to solving the stationary Schrödinger Equation, at the fixed initial time t_0 , and obtaining a solution to Eq. (2.3.4) for the time dependent Hamiltonian. In the next chapter a numerical method for the solution of Eq. (2.3.4) is derived.

2.4 A SIMPLIFIED HYDROGEN HAMILTONIAN

In further sections only a simplified and one-dimensional Hamiltonian is discussed

$$\hat{H} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} - \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0\sqrt{r^2+1}}. \quad (2.4.1)$$

This simplification is achieved by using the Born-Oppenheimer approximation, where the atomic core is assumed to be fixed, and only the electric component of the problem is considered. A further approximation is the treatment of only the radial component in one dimension. In order to successfully handle the resulting singularity at $r = 0$, the modified potential $-\frac{1}{\sqrt{x^2+1}}$ is introduced. To justify the selection of the model potential see Fig. 2.4.1.

Figure 2.4.1: A visual comparison the the coulomb and model potential. The error becomes increasingly small as r approaches infinity. As the Coulomb potential diverges at the coordinate origin, the model potential begins to deviate.

2.5 TIME DEPENDENT HAMILTONIAN

In this section, a disturbance term will be added to the time-independent Hamiltonian \hat{H}_0

$$\hat{H} = \hat{H}_0 + V_1(t). \quad (2.5.1)$$

Here, we claim that the introduced addend vanishes at t_0 , so that the initial state $|\psi(t_0)\rangle$ will be a stationary state of \hat{H}_0 . For $t > t_0$ $V_1(x, t)$, is assumed to be varying very slowly in time so for $\tau \ll t$, it holds that $V_1(x, t + \tau) \approx V_1(x, t)$ and can be a model for an electromagnetic wave (see Ref. [17], p. 1291) of the form

$$V_1(x, t) = A_0 \cdot \sin(\omega t - kx), \quad (2.5.2)$$

where A_0 is a constant amplitude. An envelope in the spatial and time domain should be applied to ensure slow variation in the disturbance term. One can think of an envelope in the form of two Gaussians

$$g(x, t) = e^{-a(t-t_0)^2} \cdot e^{-b(x-x_0)^2}. \quad (2.5.3)$$

Using an appropriate full width half maximum (FWHM) condition for the time dependent Gaussian, ensures that the Hamiltonian stays approximately constant for small time changes τ . In the spatial domain, the corresponding Gaussian will only affect an area, where the probability density of the stationary states will be non-zero.

Figure 2.5.1: Time disturbance term of the form $V_1(x, t) = A_0 \cdot \sin(\omega t - kx) \cdot e^{-a_0(t-t_0)^2} \cdot e^{-b(x-x_0)^2}$. The parameters are $\lambda = 60$ a.u., $a = 6.93110^{-7}$ a.u. $^{-3}$, $t_0 = 2500$ a.u., $b = 0.007$ a.u. $^{-2}$, $x_0 = 0$ a.u. and $A_0 = 1.0$ (a.u.).

3 NUMERICAL METHODS

The stationary as well as the time-dependent Schrödinger Equation can only be solved analytically for a limited amount of systems. In general, a variety of numerical techniques are necessary to find at least approximate solutions with an acceptable error. In this chapter we introduce the required solver algorithms for the stationary problem and the time-dependent system. Thereafter, a description of the implementation is presented and first results are shown, to verify the accuracy of the code.

3.1 THE DISCRETE HAMILTONIAN

In this section, the one-dimensional Schrödinger equation will be the main focus

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \psi(x, t) = \left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + V(x, t) \right) \psi(x, t), \quad (3.1.1)$$

where $x \in \mathbb{R}$. The question which arises here is: How can Eq. (3.1.1) be solved numerically? First of all, it is necessary to transform the continuous derivatives into a discrete form. This can be achieved by the applying definition of the derivative

$$\frac{d}{dx} f(x) = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x+h) - f(x)}{h}. \quad (3.1.2)$$

To gain a numerical approximation of the derivative, the limit is simply left out. Thus, for smaller h the result will be more precise. It can be shown, that this procedure, known as the forward difference method, creates an numerical error of order $\mathcal{O}(h)$. Since Eq. (3.1.1) contains a second order derivative, it is appropriate to derive an expression for this case

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2} f(x) = \lim_{h' \rightarrow 0} \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x+h+h') - f(x+h') - (f(x+h) - f(x))}{h'h} \quad (3.1.3)$$

$$= \lim_{h' \rightarrow 0} \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x+h+h') + f(x) - 2f(x+h')}{h'h} \quad (3.1.4)$$

$$\approx \frac{f(x+2h) + f(x) - 2f(x+h)}{h^2}. \quad (3.1.5)$$

Now this approximation is applied to the Hamiltonian. One has to define an interval $[a, b] \subset \mathbb{R}$, where the boundary conditions for $\psi(x, t)$ are approximately satisfied. This means that

$\psi(a, t) \approx \psi(b, t) \approx 0$. It is now necessary to define also a discrete grid of N equidistant points, on the interval $[a, b]$. To achieve this, we define $\Delta x = \frac{b-a}{N}$ and write $x_i = a + \Delta x \cdot i$. The following sections will make use the notation $\varphi(x_i) = \varphi_i$. The derived scheme can now be applied to the stationary Schrödinger Equation.

$$\hat{H} \varphi(x) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \varphi(x) + V(x)\varphi(x) \quad (3.1.6)$$

$$\approx -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\varphi_{i+1} + \varphi_{i-1} - 2\varphi_i}{\Delta x^2} + V_i \varphi_i \quad (3.1.7)$$

Note that here the indices were shifted back by one spatial step.

The previous expression can be interpreted as a matrix-vector equation. Therefore, the Hamiltonian can be written as the following matrix

$$\hat{H} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m\Delta x^2} (\mathbb{I}_N^+ + \mathbb{I}_N^- - 2\mathbb{I}_N) + \hat{V}, \quad (3.1.8)$$

where

- \mathbb{I}_N is the $N \times N$ Identity matrix
- \mathbb{I}_N^\pm are $N \times N$ matrices, which either have entries of 1 on their upper(+) or lower(-) diagonals
- \hat{V} is the Potential matrix which only has entries on its main diagonal and is of the form $V_{ij} = V(x_i)\delta_{ij}$, where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker Delta.

3.2 COMPUTATION OF THE STATIONARY STATES BY USING NUMEROVS ALGORITHM

Before we begin to derive a numerical scheme for Eq. (3.1.1), a method to solve the stationary Schrödinger Equation has to be established first. In particular we are interested in the eigenvalues E_k and eigenstates φ_k subject to

$$E_k \varphi_k(x) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \varphi_k(x) + V(x)\varphi_k(x). \quad (3.2.1)$$

To obtain physical meaningful results, the wave-function φ needs to approach zero for $x \rightarrow \pm\infty$. Also, φ_k needs to satisfy the norm constraints $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |\varphi_k(x)|^2 dx = 1$. The solution to Eq. (3.2.1) will depend on the energy as a constant parameter. Since in general, an analytical expression for the system energy cannot be found, energy E_k and φ_k have to be determined numerically. The Numerov algorithm to solve Eq. (3.2.1) seems to be an appropriate choice, because of its high order of accuracy h^4 [18, 19]. In case of the stationary Schrödinger Equation, the algorithm is given by

$$(1 + f_{n+1}) \varphi_{n+1} = 2\varphi_n (1 - 5f_n) - \varphi_{n-1} (1 + f_{n-1}), \quad (3.2.2)$$

where $f(x) = \frac{\Delta x^2}{12} \frac{2m}{\hbar^2} (E - V(x))$. The spatial dimension has to be limited to an interval $[a, b] \subset \mathbb{R}$. Therefore, a and b have to be chosen so that φ_k is close to zero at $x = b$ and $\varphi_k < \infty$ at $x = a$. The next step is now to choose another interval of Energies $[E_{\min}, E_{\max}]$, so that $E - V(b) < 0 \forall E \in [E_{\min}, E_{\max}]$, since we are only interested in the bound states of the system. In the resulting classically forbidden region, we expect the wave-function to decay exponentially. It is reasonable to assume that the resulting wave-functions will approach 0 fast enough at the boundary $x = b$ and has a finite value at $x = a$.

The next step is to choose an equidistant discretization for both the energy and the spatial interval. The discretization steps therefore are $\delta E = \frac{E_{\max} - E_{\min}}{N_E}$ and $\Delta x = \frac{b-a}{N_x}$. To understand the further proceedings, it should be noted that solutions of Eq. (3.2.1) can only diverge to $\pm\infty$ or converge to 0.

This result leads to the following idea: If the solution φ_{E_n} diverges to $\pm\infty$ and another solution φ_{E_m} diverges to $\mp\infty$, at least one solution φ_{E_k} , with $E_k \in [E_n, E_m]$, can be determined, which converges to 0 fast enough and constitutes a solution of Eq. (3.2.1).

Thus, an algorithm can be formulated:

1. Choose and discretize the intervals $[a, b]$, $[E_{\min}, E_{\max}]$ in a reasonably accurate way
2. Calculate φ_{E_i} for all discrete energy values E_i , with the Numerov algorithm. To receive solutions which are non zero, the value $\varphi_{E_i}(a)$ can be set to an arbitrary value manually, as long as it is consistent with the predefined boundary condition. For instance if $\varphi_{E_i}(a) = 0$, $\varphi_{E_i}(a)$ can be set to 10^{-7} , since smaller values would affect the machine accuracy.
3. Run the bisection algorithm over all solutions φ_{E_i} at $x = b$. If the bisection finds a zero, the tuple (E_j, φ_{E_j}) is a solution to our problem.

Bear in mind that the solutions of this algorithm are not necessarily normalized. Therefore, the detected solutions must be multiplied with a constant so that $\int_a^b \varphi_{E_i}^*(x) \varphi_{E_i}(x) dx = 1$. A major disadvantage of this approach is its computational demand. For each discrete energy step the solution φ_{E_i} needs to be calculated. Since the Numerov algorithm "marches through" all the discrete spatial nodes, its computational demand is directly proportional to the number of those nodes N_x . If N_E is the number of discrete energy nodes, the overall computational demand is $\mathcal{O}(N_x \cdot N_E)$. For higher accuracy computations $N_x \approx N_E$ and therefore we get a $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ computational complexity. Counting in the bisection method, which needs to search at worst $\approx N_E$ solutions, the computational complexity rises to $\mathcal{O}(N^3)$. To reduce this computational demand, a parallel method should be developed.

3.3 DERIVATION OF THE CRANK-NICOLSON ALGORITHM

3.3.1 Case of time-independent Hamiltonian

The previous section provided an approach to calculate the energy levels as well as the corresponding wave-functions for an arbitrary time-independent potential. The next problem is to find a solution for the TDSE for any arbitrary time-dependent potential. This can be done by the Crank-Nicolson algorithm. Section 2.3 provided the necessary information on how the TDSE can be transformed from a partial differential equation into an homogeneous ordinary differential equation describing the time evolution operator U . For time-independent potentials a solution can be achieved easily, since the time evolution operator becomes, for a small time interval $\tau = t - t_0$,

$$U(t, t_0) = e^{-\frac{i\tau \hat{H}}{\hbar}}. \quad (3.3.1)$$

Now the time evolution operator can be approximated as in Ref [20]

$$U(t, t_0) = e^{-\frac{i\tau \hat{H}}{\hbar}} \approx \frac{1 - \frac{i\tau}{2\hbar} \hat{H}}{1 + \frac{i\tau}{2\hbar} \hat{H}}. \quad (3.3.2)$$

Applying this to a state $\psi(x, t)$ will result in the expression

$$\left(1 + \frac{i\tau}{2\hbar} \hat{H}\right) \psi(x, t + \tau) = \left(1 - \frac{i\tau}{2\hbar} \hat{H}\right) \psi(x, t). \quad (3.3.3)$$

As stated in Ref. [20], the Hamiltonian has to be independent of time in order to use the so called Cayley form of the time-evolution operator. In later sections it is necessary to evolve a state with an explicitly time-dependent Hamiltonian. Thus, a derivation of the scheme including this case has to be performed.

3.3.2 Case of time dependent Hamiltonian

The case of a time-dependent Hamiltonian needs to be approached from the TDSE instead of the operator Eq. (2.3.4). As in Ref. [21] p. 223, the idea is to use a half discrete step-size in a way so that a complementary expression to Eq. (3.3.3) is obtained.

Starting with the TDSE for a state $|\psi\rangle$, the use of an Euler forward discretization with a half-sized time step will hold an expression for the infinitesimal time-operator

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} |\psi(t)\rangle = -\frac{i}{\hbar} \hat{H}(t) |\psi(t)\rangle \quad (3.3.4)$$

$$\frac{|\psi(t + \frac{\tau}{2})\rangle - |\psi(t)\rangle}{\frac{\tau}{2}} \approx -\frac{i}{\hbar} \hat{H}(t) |\psi(t)\rangle \quad (3.3.5)$$

$$|\psi(t + \frac{\tau}{2})\rangle = |\psi(t)\rangle - \frac{i\tau}{2\hbar} \hat{H}(t) |\psi(t)\rangle \quad (3.3.6)$$

$$|\psi(t + \frac{\tau}{2})\rangle = \left(1 - \frac{i\tau}{2\hbar} \hat{H}(t)\right) |\psi(t)\rangle. \quad (3.3.7)$$

Next, an Euler backwards differentiation is applied to the TDSE, which now describes a state $|\psi\rangle$ at the point in time $t + \tau$.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} |\psi(t + \tau)\rangle = -\frac{i}{\hbar} \hat{H}(t + \tau) |\psi(t + \tau)\rangle \quad (3.3.8)$$

$$\frac{|\psi(t + \tau)\rangle - |\psi(t + \frac{\tau}{2})\rangle}{\frac{\tau}{2}} \approx -\frac{i}{\hbar} \hat{H}(t + \tau) |\psi(t + \tau)\rangle \quad (3.3.9)$$

$$-|\psi(t + \frac{\tau}{2})\rangle = -|\psi(t + \tau)\rangle - \frac{i\tau}{2\hbar} \hat{H}(t + \tau) |\psi(t + \tau)\rangle \quad (3.3.10)$$

$$|\psi(t + \frac{\tau}{2})\rangle = \left(1 + \frac{i\tau}{2\hbar} \hat{H}(t + \tau)\right) |\psi(t + \tau)\rangle \quad (3.3.11)$$

Inserting Eq. (3.3.11) in Eq. (3.3.7) will result again in the Crank-Nicolson algorithm for a time-dependent Hamiltonian.

$$\left(1 + \frac{i\tau}{2\hbar} \hat{H}(t + \tau)\right) |\psi(t + \tau)\rangle = \left(1 - \frac{i\tau}{2\hbar} \hat{H}(t)\right) |\psi(t)\rangle \quad (3.3.12)$$

Eq. (3.3.12) is coherent with Eq. (3.3.3) and it can be shown, as in Ref. [20], that the error of this scheme in the time domain is $\mathcal{O}(\tau^3)$. Also, one can show, that the scheme is unitary and therefore preserves the norm (see Ref. [21] p.223).

3.4 IMPLEMENTATION OF THE CRANK-NICOLSON SCHEME

In this chapter, the implementation details of the previous developed methods are described and discussed. Also, parallelization schemes of the used algorithms are explained and evaluated.

3.4.1 Used tools

The implementation makes use of the C++ programming language. For parallelization the NVIDIA CUDA toolset was used, which makes it possible to implement the derived schemes on GPUs, a massively parallel architecture. As external library component, the Thrust template library was used. Like the C++ standard template library, Thrust provides a vector data structure which can be defined on CPU or GPU memory. The output of the calculated data is collected by the HDF5 library. Data analysis is performed using the script-language Python in combination with the libraries Matplotlib and Numpy.

3.4.2 Identifying the simulation components

The goal of writing a general purpose and high performance simulation is best achieved by finding the most general way of describing a simulation procedure. An implementation which only supports one type of system, would require a lot of code to be rewritten unnecessarily if the internal components are not decoupled enough. A favourable way of implementing the given situation is to identify components or modules, which are required to realize the simulation process, without making any assumption on their actual implementation. This means for the problem at hand: A potential $V(x, t)$ is given as well as pre-defined boundary conditions. Also a set of grid parameters (spatial or time domain) is provided. From given information the stationary states for $V(x, t_0)$, the corresponding energy, and the time evolution in the potential $V(x, t)$ must be calculated. The problem statement allows the identification of the following components:

- A parameter component which saves the simulation parameters
- A solver of the stationary Schrödinger Equation for an arbitrary potential
- A solver of the time dependent Schrödinger Equation
- A coordination component of the simulation, which handles parameter passing and simulation structure.

Obviously, the components are highly dependent on the dimension and structure of the given problem. Even though, the program currently only implements one-dimensional cases, it is useful to think about a general solution, because future additions of features will get easier and less error-prone. For instance, the utilization of a one-dimensional set of parameters will be incompatible with a two-dimensional solver of the stationary Schrödinger equation. Therefore, the parameter set already determines which solvers are allowed. For a more clear idea, how the components interact with each other, see Fig. 3.4.1.

Figure 3.4.1: Component model of the implementation. The Simulation Master component is provided with the memory reference of the Parameter Set. After passing the memory location of the Parameter Set to the Static Solver the solve command is issued. Stationary states are then calculated by the Static Solver and one of them is returned to the Simulation Master component. The Simulation Master then again passes the Parameter Set, as well as the calculated state, to the Dynamic Solver and issues its solve command. The solve command now calculates the time evolution of the state inside the potentials $V(x, t)$. Output can be implemented by the individual components internally.

The described components can be directly implemented as C++ classes. In this case, the components can be interpreted as abstract classes, from which the actual implemented algorithms

inherit. This results in the fact, that each solver will have its own type. So the solver components can be viewed as policies of the Simulation Master, see Ref. [22]. As an example of the inheritance scheme see Fig. 3.4.2 and Fig. 3.4.3.

Figure 3.4.2: Inheritance class diagram of the Parameter Set.

Figure 3.4.3: Inheritance class diagram of the Static Solver component.

The arising incompatibilities caused by the simulation dimension can be tackled by forcing static and dynamic solvers to include a parameter member of their corresponding dimension. The simulation is now decoupled from the actual implementation of both solvers, dimension and system. Note that the potential has to be implemented by the solvers themselves, which is not optimal but practical.

3.4.3 Parallel calculation of stationary states

The scheme to find the stationary states of a system, which was developed in Section 3.2, has a high computational demand. Therefore, using a parallel approach is necessary, to reduce computation time. It is challenging to find possible ways for parallelization within the Numerov algorithm itself. Looking at Eq. (3.2.2) shows that each iteration depends on the results of its two predecessors. Using one kernel for each iteration is useless, since each one of them has to wait until its predecessor is finished. However, recalling that the procedure also requires an energy grid, to calculate the stationary states as a parameter, opens a possibility for parallelism. Calculating the solutions φ_{E_j} is not influenced by any other ongoing computation. As a result, each CUDA kernel will be assigned an energy E_j to calculate the corresponding wave-function φ_{E_j} . To emphasize this idea, Fig. 3.4.4, shows the naive parallel execution scheme inside the GPU memory.

Figure 3.4.4: Naive parallelization for detecting the stationary states of a system. The figure shows how the kernels interact with the GPU memory. The total required memory is an array of length $N_x \cdot N_E$. Each wave-function is assigned to a slice of length N_x . For instance, wave-function n refers to the array indices $n \cdot N_x$ to $n \cdot N_x + (N_x - 1)$. To ensure that the boundary conditions are satisfied, the first corresponding memory cell is set to the value 0 and the second one is set to an arbitrary small value, like 10^{-7} . Each kernel will now calculate its corresponding wave-function φ_{E_n} . The parallel execution is achieved by launching N_E kernels on the device, which will calculate all solutions simultaneously. A disadvantage of this approach is the enormous amount of required memory.

After the calculation is done, the resulting array is loaded into CPU memory and bisected to detect all of the stationary states. A disadvantage of this approach, is its enormous memory consumption for large grids. If using a grid size of $N_E = N_x = 10^6$ nodes, the required memory would be about 7 Terabytes. To determine the energy of a system with the highest possible precision, an energy grid of the size $N_E = 10^8$ is required. A way to circumvent this problem, is to slice the whole procedure into calculate-able chunks. We define a chunk size χ and slice the energy-grid into chunks of length χ . If $N_E \cdot N_x \bmod \chi \neq 0$, the last chunk will have the length $(N_E \cdot N_x) \bmod \chi$. Now the procedure has to be adapted: It is now only necessary to load an array of the current chunk-length l_c into GPU memory and execute the parallelization scheme as before. For an optimal speed-up, the number of launched kernels on the GPU should be equal to the number of wave-functions in a chunk. Also, when running the bisection over each chunk, the last wave-function of the previous chunk must be included to ensure that the sign change did not occur on the border of a chunk. The algorithm is summarized in the listing below.

Algorithm 1 Parallel computation of the stationary states

```

1: set  $\chi$  as chunk-length
2: set cache : Array of length  $\chi$ 
3: fill cache with initial values
4: set chunk : Array of length  $\chi$ 
5:  $E_0 = 0$ 
6:  $dE = V_{\min}/N_E$ 
7: for  $i < N_E$  do
8:   if  $i + \chi > N_x \cdot N_E$  then
9:      $\chi = (N_x \cdot N_E) - i$ 
10:    set chunk to length  $\chi$ 
11:    set cache to length  $\chi$  and fill initial values
12:  end if
13:  load values of cache into GPU memory
14:   $E = dE \cdot i$ 
15:  launch  $\frac{\chi}{N_x}$  kernels to calculate the stationary states
16:  copy results into chunk
17:  if  $i > \chi$  then
18:    run bisection on chunk and  $\varphi_{\text{last}}$ 
19:  else
20:    run bisection on chunk
21:  end if
22:  save last  $\varphi$  in chunk as  $\varphi_{\text{last}}$ 
23:   $i += \chi$ 
24: end for

```

The results of this implementation are shown in Fig. 3.4.5

Figure 3.4.5: The wave-functions inside the core-potential $-\frac{1}{\sqrt{x^2+1}}$ at the heights of their corresponding eigenenergies. The other parameters are: $x_{\max} = -x_{\min} = 30$ a.u., $N_x = 10^5$, $N_E = 10^8$, $E_{\min} = -1$ a.u. and $E_{\max} = 0$ a.u.

To obtain the most precise physical results, the energy lattice has to be as fine as possible. Obviously, there is a computational limit on how precise the energy can be determined. In this case, the machine precision as well as the resulting computational time pose an upper limit on how

large N_E can be chosen. Here, the maximum achievable energy lattice is $N_E = 10^8$, since the resulting energy-step $\delta E = \frac{E_{\max} - E_{\min}}{N_E}$ will be of the same order as the limit of the floating point arithmetic of the computer.

A further problem is that the states, especially for lower energies, will start to diverge for larger spatial values as shown in Fig. 3.4.6. This effect poses a huge problem, since it makes the scheme unusable for lower energy levels, as those diverging solutions contradict the boundary conditions. We now have to find a way to correct this effect. One has to bear in mind that this is not caused by the Numerov method, but by the limited resolution of the energy lattice.

Figure 3.4.6: The resulting divergence of an energy level. This is caused by the limited precision to determine the system energy. It is a known result, that the Schrödinger Equation only produces states, which will diverge to $\pm\infty$ or converge to 0. In order to find the exact solution of the problem, one has to choose E infinitely precise. In our case, the corresponding energy still was not chosen precisely enough. In addition computation time rises with larger energy grids to an unreasonable amount.

Taking a look at Eq. (3.2.2)

$$(1 + f_{n+1}) \varphi_{n+1} = 2\varphi_n (1 - 5f_n) - \varphi_{n-1} (1 + f_{n-1}), \quad (3.4.1)$$

suggests that the forward iteration scheme can be converted into a backwards iterating algorithm as well. One simply finds:

$$(1 + f_{n-1}) \varphi_{n-1} = 2\varphi_n (1 - 5f_n) - \varphi_{n+1} (1 + f_{n+1}). \quad (3.4.2)$$

If the assumption holds that the solution detected by the bisection methods is indeed a physical one, a solution which was computed by a backwards iteration will have satisfied boundary conditions for $x \rightarrow b$ of $[a, b]$ and will diverge for $x \rightarrow a$. Fig. 3.4.7 shows that this is indeed the case.

Figure 3.4.7: Backwards iterated stationary state. The graph also shows a slight divergence for $x \rightarrow -30$ a.u. . Therefore, the same effect as in the forward iteration scheme of the Numerov algorithm occurs.

From this observation, a method to circumvent those divergences can be developed.

The forwards Numerov iteration will only satisfy the boundary conditions in the interval $[a, b]$ on the left, whereas the backwards iteration will enforce the boundary condition on the right side of $[a, b]$. The reason for this is that on both starting points one has to set the first gridpoint to 0 and its successor to an arbitrary small value. For the same energies, both iterations should calculate the same resulting wave-function φ_E . The only difference between those function will be that the forward iteration diverges for $x \rightarrow b$ and the backwards iteration will diverge for $x \rightarrow a$. After the parallel calculation of an stationary state $\varphi_{E,f}$, which is calculated by a forwards iteration, the wave-function to its corresponding energy $\varphi_{E,b}$ can be calculated by a backwards iteration. Let $\varepsilon > 0$, going through the calculated values of $\varphi_{E,f}$ and $\varphi_{E,b}$ from b to a , if $|\varphi_{E,b} - \varphi_{E,f}| \leq \varepsilon$ at an index j , simply overwrite the values of $\varphi_{E,f}$ with $\varphi_{E,b}$ from the indices j to N_x . The corrected graph $\varphi_{E,c}$ will have none of the divergences, which were occurring before. Fig. 3.4.8 shows the result of this method, which was calculated from the state in Fig. 3.4.6 and Fig. 3.4.7.

Figure 3.4.8: The proposed corrected scheme applied to the wave-functions calculated in Figs. 3.4.6 and 3.4.7. The wave-function now satisfies the boundary conditions on both interval borders.

The method is also required to correct errors in the Crank-Nicolson scheme, which is discussed in the following section.

3.4.4 Time evolution on GPUs using the Crank Nicolson algorithm

Before discussing the actual implementation of the Crank-Nicolson algorithm it is described, how the scheme can be realized numerically. The derived formula from Eq. (3.3.12), in spatial representation and atomic units is

$$\left(1 + \frac{i\tau}{2\hbar} \hat{H}(t + \tau)\right) \psi(x, t + \tau) = \left(1 - \frac{i\tau}{2\hbar} \hat{H}(t)\right) \psi(x, t),$$

for a particle of mass m_e . The Hamiltonian can be used in its discrete form as already derived. One has to remember, that the time now has to be discretized too. Such time discretization follows similarly to the steps taken before. Here, τ refers to the small time-step. We define the following notation: $\psi(x_{\min} + \Delta x \cdot i, t_{\min} + \tau \cdot j) = \psi_i^j$.

All of the expressions above can now be interpreted as a matrix equation

$$\left(\mathbb{I} + \frac{i\tau}{2} \left[-\frac{1}{2\Delta x^2} (\mathbb{I}^+ + \mathbb{I} - 2\mathbb{I}) + \hat{V}_i^{j+1}\right]\right) \psi_i^{j+1} = \left(\mathbb{I} - \frac{i\tau}{2} \left[-\frac{1}{2\Delta x^2} (\mathbb{I}^+ + \mathbb{I} - 2\mathbb{I}) + \hat{V}_i^j\right]\right) \psi_i^j. \quad (3.4.3)$$

Using the matrix vector product, the right hand side of Eq. (3.4.3) becomes

$$r_i := \psi_i^j - \frac{i\tau}{2} \left[-\frac{1}{2\Delta x^2} (\psi_{i+1}^j + \psi_{i-1}^j - 2\psi_i^j) + V_i^j \psi_i^j\right]. \quad (3.4.4)$$

Obviously, the operator on the left hand side is a matrix of the form

$$\tilde{U} = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & b_1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ c_2 & a_2 & b_2 & & \vdots \\ 0 & & \ddots & & 0 \\ \vdots & & c_{n-1} & a_{n-1} & b_{n-1} \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & c_n & a_n \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.4.5)$$

Now, taking a further look on the lower and upper diagonal, it is obvious that both only contain the constant values

$$c_i = b_i = -\frac{i\tau}{4\Delta x^2}. \quad (3.4.6)$$

Entries on the main diagonal are

$$a_i = 1 + \frac{i\tau}{2\Delta x^2} + \frac{i\tau}{2} V_i^{j+1}. \quad (3.4.7)$$

The problem is now to solve the linear system

$$\tilde{U} \psi^j = r. \quad (3.4.8)$$

For this kind of systems a wide range of algorithms exists since \tilde{U} is tridiagonal. The most common choice would be the Thomas algorithm. But a huge problem of the scheme is that the procedure it describes is quintessentially serial and therefore difficult to parallelize on GPUs. It is

possible to derive and implement a solver on GPUs, but a large amount of work will go into optimizing the algorithm for the GPU architecture. For this work, the algorithm proposed and implemented in Ref. [23] is an appropriate choice. Another possibility is the solver function provided by NVIDIA's CUSPARSE library. The underlying algorithm is a hybrid between cyclic reduction and parallel cyclic reduction. For further explanation of the solving schemes one can refer to Ref. [24].

The idea of the implemented Crank Nicolson algorithm is described below.

Algorithm 2 The parallel Crank-Nicolson algorithm on GPUs

- 1: Get a stationary state which describes $\psi(x, t_0) = \psi^0$ and set it as ψ_n
 - 2: Create the upper, lower and main diagonal of the matrix, which is represented by 3 complex typed arrays of length N_x
 - 3: Fill the upper and lower diagonal with the values from Eq. (3.4.6)
 - 4: for $i < N_t$ do
 - 5: Calculate the right hand side vector \vec{r} described in Eq. (3.4.4), using ψ_n and $t_i = i * \tau$
 - 6: Calculate the main diagonal described by Eq. (3.4.7)
 - 7: Pass the diagonals and \vec{r} to the tridiagonal solver and obtain ψ^{i+1}
 - 8: Set ψ^{i+1} to ψ_n
 - 9: end for
-

An exemplary result of the implementation is shown in Fig. 3.4.9.

Figure 3.4.9: Time Evolution of the ψ_2 state inside the potential $V(x) = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{1+x^2}}$. All four figures show the imaginary and real part of ψ_2 separately. The spatial parameters were identical to those in Fig. 3.4.5: $x_{\text{xmax}} = 30$ a.u., $x_{\text{min}} = -30$ a.u. and $N_x = 10^5$, whereas the time grid had the specifications $t_{\text{max}} = 40$ a.u., $t_{\text{min}} = 0$ and $N_t = 10^6$. The time step size is therefore $\tau = 4.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$

To test the time evolution, one can use the time-evolution operator in the case of time-independent Hamiltonian. For a qualitative comparison of the numerical and analytical result, see Fig. 3.4.10.

Figure 3.4.10: Qualitative comparison between a) the numerical and b) the analytical time evolution. The developed wave-function is the first excited state above the ground state. For this case the identical time step was chosen as in Fig. 3.4.9

For a more clear view, Fig. 3.4.11 shows the error norm between the imaginary and real part of the wave-function before.

Figure 3.4.11: Differences between the real and imaginary part of the analytic and numerical wave-function of the state used in Fig. 3.4.9 and Fig. 3.4.10. Both imaginary and real errors are reasonably small. The simulation used a spatial grid resolution of $N_x = 10^5$ nodes.

If the stationary state does not exactly satisfy the boundary conditions, one will observe that the Crank-Nicolson scheme will produce artefacts which will lead to wrong results. The situation in Fig. 3.4.12 is the following: The interval has been changed to $[0, 15]$ and for better visibility of the spread of artefacts during the procedure, the number of spatial grid nodes is reduced to 1000 and $N_t = 10000$. This situation is similar to the radial hydrogen problem, which required that the distance $r > 0$. The wave-function is expected to be 0 for $x < 0$, so the used potential is

$$V(x) = \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{\sqrt{x^2+1}} & \text{for } 0 \leq x \leq b \\ \infty & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (3.4.9)$$

It is an implicit assumption and describes a similar situation to the particle in a infinite potential well. In this situation, the wave-function is only solved for cases where $V(x) < \infty$. The same situation applies here as well. We force the wave-function to be zero outside the chosen interval and to achieve this, the potential has to be infinite. The discontinuities will cause an artefact to be produced, but it is compensated if ψ converges to zero slowly, since the Crank-Nicolson algorithm includes terms of the form $V(x)\psi(x)$. Fig. 3.4.12 shows that all graphs do not include any significant error on their right border, but since the graphs rise quickly at the coordinate origin, the artefact is not compensated by the wave-function.

To circumvent those errors, an asymmetric box starting at the origin must not be used. Though the energies of both asymmetric and symmetric box states will be identical, due to the way they are detected. This also justifies the correction of occurring divergences in the previous section. If a divergence occurs on the borders, an artefact will get created during the time evolution as Fig. 3.4.13 shows. So the error correction for the boundary values is essential for a correct time evolution.

Figure 3.4.12: Artefact spread in the imaginary part during the Crank Nicolson procedure. Graph a) shows that the first time steps already produces a relative large artefact, for the ground state. This artefact spreads through the curve in later time steps, as each time step is dependent on its predecessor. Note that the divergence correcting procedure was not applied to this graph, since the boundary condition at $x = 15$ a.u. is satisfied. The time step parameter was $\Delta t = 0.05$ a.u. .

Figure 3.4.13: Artefacts created during time evolution, because of unsatisfied boundary conditions.

4 NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DATA ANALYSIS

This chapter shows the results of different time disturbance terms applied to the Hamiltonian introduced in Section 2.4. A general goal is to observe a state transition from some bound state of the system into e.g. a free state. At first we can recall the disturbance with the additional Gaussian envelopes from Section 2.5

$$V_1(x, t) = A_0 \cdot e^{-a(t-t_0)^2} \cdot e^{-b(x-x_0)^2} \cdot \sin(\omega t). \quad (4.0.1)$$

For all simulations the identical box as in Fig. 3.4.5 has been chosen with $x_{\min} = -30$ a.u. $= -x_{\max}$, $N_x = 10^5$. The time domain has the parameter set $N_t = 10^5$, $t_{\min} = 0$ a.u. and $t_{\max} = 5000$ a.u. . Since the Hamiltonian has to vary slowly in time, the parameters a and b of both Gaussians in the disturbance potential have to be chosen appropriately. Both parameters are given by

$$a = \frac{\ln(2)}{(t - t_0)^2}, \quad b = \frac{\ln(2)}{(x - x_0)^2}. \quad (4.0.2)$$

As the disturbance will have most effect on areas where the probability density reaches its spatial maximum, x_0 is set to zero a.u. . To meet the slowly varying condition of the Hamiltonian, the t_0 parameter is settled in the middle of the time interval at $t_0 = 2500$ a.u. . A first result is shown in Fig. 4.0.1. It clearly shows how a stationary state is resolved into a unbound one by the strong disturbance term in the Hamiltonian. The model potential does not cause a clear visible probability current after the pulse fades. Most of the probability is now non zero even around the boxes borders. Therefore, the question arises, if the total probability is a conserved quantity over time. A simple way to test this claim, is to simply plot the integrated probability over time as in Fig. 4.0.2. Obviously, except for smaller deviations, the total probability is conserved during the whole simulation. A visualization of the probability density at the maximum size of our disturbance term is shown in Fig. 4.0.3. The distribution now has maxima even in the previously classical forbidden region. The breakup point of the bound state seems to happen rather rapidly after the FWHM of the Gaussian envelope has been reached. If one reduces the FWHM of $g(t)$, the model potential will cause the state to partially flow back into its initial position. This effect is shown in Fig. 4.0.4, where the FWHM has been set to $t = 2250$ a.u. .

Figure 4.0.1: Time evolution of the probability density with the Hamiltonian $H_0 + V_1(x, t)$, H_0 is defined in Section 2.4. The evolved state is identical to the one discussed in Section 3.4.4. The parameters were set to be the following: $N_x = 10^5$, $x_{\max} = -x_{\min} = 30$ a.u., $t_{\min} = 0$ a.u., $t_{\max} = 5000$ a.u., $N_t = 10^5$ and $\lambda = 10000$ a.u.. Whereas the parameters of the corresponding Gaussians are: $x_0 = 0$ a.u., $t_0 = 2500$ a.u.. The FWHM x and t locations were chosen as $x_{\text{FWHM}} = 20$ a.u. and $t_{\text{FWHM}} = 1500$ a.u.. The overall amplitude was $A = 1.0$ a.u.. The graph shows clearly how the stationary state is dissolved by the rising disturbance term. The Gaussian time envelope is shown in arbitrary units as the blue graph.

Figure 4.0.2: The integrate probability density plotted over time. Comparing to the Gaussian envelope in Fig. 4.0.1 holds, that the time-dependent potential seems to cause small disturbances of the total probability in the volume. Those disturbances are in a small enough scale, so that the total probability is approximately conserved over time.

Figure 4.0.3: The disturbed wavefunction during the maximum pulse at $t = 25000$ a.u. . As one can easily observe, almost the complete probability has been scattered to the classical forbidden region.

Figure 4.0.4: The identical simulation as in Fig. 4.0.1, with the only alteration being the point in time, where the FWHM is reached, was reduced to $t = 2250$ a.u. . The model Coulomb potential then causes a probability current back to the initial maxima of the state.

In terms of speed-up, the used tridiagonal solver on the GPU has been benchmarked against a serial CPU implementation of the Thomas algorithm, since the solution of the linear system is the most time-consuming part of the time evolution. The test system used a GTX 680 graphics card and an Intel Core i5-3750K CPU. The benchmark used identical parameters as in Fig. 4.0.1 and averaged the time each solver took to generate a solution over 1000 time-steps. The standard deviation was calculated according to the formula

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^N (t_i - \bar{t})^2}, \quad (4.0.3)$$

where t_i refers to each individual measuring point, N is the total number of measured values, and \bar{t} is the mean value of the measurement. Thus, the results are shown in the table below.

Table 4.0.1: Performance comparison between the pure serial CPU based Thomas algorithm and the SPIKE algorithm proposed in Ref. [25]. Again the parameters were: $N_x = 10^5$, $x_{\max} = -x_{\min} = 30$ a.u., $t_{\min} = 0$ a.u., $t_{\max} = 5000$ a.u., $N_t = 10^5$. The time disturbance term was configured to $\lambda = 10000$ a.u., $x_0 = 0$ a.u., $t_0 = 2500$ a.u., $x_{\text{FWHM}} = 20$ a.u., $t_{\text{FWHM}} = 1500$ a.u., and $A = 1.0$ a.u., even though those parameters will not influence the performance of the simulation in any kind.

Solver	Average solving time (ms)	Standard deviation (ms)
Thomas Serial	85.2542	0.007
GPU Based	2.5639	0.0594

This results in a overall performance gain for each solver call of factor 33.25.

5 SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION

A general strategy, how quantum mechanical systems can be simulated has been proposed. A big advantage of the implementation is its efficient runtime, which is about 12 minutes for the time evolution simulations on the system described in Chapter 4. As mentioned in the previous chapter, the use of GPUs resulted in a performance gain of factor 33.25 for the solution of each tridiagonal system. The calculation of all stationary states takes significantly longer, since computational time rises with $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$, where n refers to both the size of selected spatial and energy lattice. Thus, the calculation takes about 9 hours for the parameter sets introduced in Section 3.4.4. While this is certainly not optimal, the used Numerov algorithm cannot be easily parallelized on GPUs. A possible alternative, which was not further investigated, is the detection of the stationary states by finding the eigenvalues of the discrete Hamiltonian first and then calculating the resulting eigenstates with the Numerov scheme. Because GPUs are very suitable architecture for this kind of computations, this idea should receive further investigation.

From a physical point of view, Chapter 4 clearly showed the transition of a stationary state into some unbound state. As shown, a shorter pulse caused the relaxation of the system, into its initial state. Bound state transitions, by changing the potentials wave frequency or amplitude, have not been observed up to this point. A result of those calculations is the qualitative visualization of ionization processes. The strong disturbance is able to lift the particle out of the potential, where it essentially becomes unbound. Further simulations have to be ran in order to find out how the disturbance frequency and amplitude alter the states, so the corresponding simulation parameters can be determined to reach such state transitions and test whether the code is indeed able to produce such transitions.

6 FUTURE WORK

A lot of additional features can be added to the existing simulation, whether it is from the technical or physical side. As already mentioned, a suitable parameter set to observe state transitions should be found. From this, quantities like state transition rates could be determined. The next step is to generalize the code to two- and three-dimensional systems. With more degrees of freedom, the Crank-Nicolson algorithm could lose its efficiency, since the resulting system is no longer tridiagonal. This would require the use of more sophisticated solvers or other time domain integration schemes as presented in Ref. [26]. After this step is completed, the addition of a many-body Hilbert space is required. If the simulations then includes the spin quantum number and indistinguishable particles, one has to consider the Pauli principle, which requires antisymmetrization of the many-body wave-function in case of Fermions or symmetrization in case of Bosons. For more accurate laser matter interactions, the Hamiltonian has to be altered in order to account for the vector potential. To expand the simulation to plasmas, environmental effects like shielding of the potential, phase-space factors and also, local field of density fluctuations have to be taken into account.

CONFIRMATION

Hiermit erkläre ich, dass ich diese Arbeit im Rahmen der Betreuung am Institut für Kern- und Teilchenphysik ohne unzulässige Hilfe Dritter verfasst und alle Quellen als solche gekennzeichnet habe.

Dresden, 11. July 2016

A APPENDIX

A.1 THE CUDA PROGRAMMING MODEL

As stated in Section 3.2 it is useful to apply a parallel algorithm to calculate the stationary states and the time evolution. A Graphics Processing Unit (GPU), as a massively parallel architecture, has the potential to reduce calculation time to a justifiable amount. As stated before, the use of NVIDIAs CUDA technology is being made. In order to understand the approach for later parallelization schemes, the knowledge of the CUDA programming model is useful.

The main difference to a serial program is the use of so called kernels. A kernel is a function, which can be executed on the GPU. Furthermore, kernels can be called from CPU (often referred to as host) in large amounts and then are executed in parallel on the GPU. Therefore, a lot of primitive computations can be executed in parallel. The highest speed is achieved when kernels execute primitive calculations independent of each other.

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